

Action of Hydrazides. Part III. Condensation of Semi- and Thiosemi-carbazide with Phenanthraquinone and its Derivatives and the Synthesis of Triazines.

BY SATISH CHANDRA DE.

The three substances semicarbazide, thiosemicarbazide and aminoguanidine are so closely related to one another in structure that they, might be expected to give similar products when condensed with one and the same substance; but nevertheless, there is a distinct difference between the action of thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide on the one hand and aminoguanidine on the other towards 1:2-diketones.

It is well known that while semicarbazide reacts with 1:2-diketones, excepting benzil, to form semicarbazones, the triazines are the sole products of the action of aminoguanidine on phenanthraquinone and other aromatic diketones (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 183). The behaviour of thiosemicarbazide towards 1:2-diketones appears not to have been investigated in most cases and to my knowledge the only evidence found in literature is that of the action of the hydrazide on benzil, the product being 3-thiol-5:6-diphenyl-1:2:4-triazine.

It has now been possible to show that thiosemicarbazide behaves exactly like semicarbazide towards phenanthraquinone and its derivatives in giving thiosemicarbazones whilst with the monoximes of the diketone and its derivatives it gives triazines. It has also been possible to convert the thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones of phenanthraquinone and its substitution products into triazines, a reaction which appears not to have been pointed out by any of the previous investigators. The formation of triazines from the thiosemicarbazones or semicarbazones probably takes place in the following way:

Though theoretically the formation of two isomeric triazines is possible from monosubstituted phenanthraquinones (depending on whether the keto-group in position 9 or 10 should first react to form the thiosemicarbazones) only one triazine is actually formed in every case. The following system of numbering the positions in the phenanthratriazines has been adopted:

(III)

(IV)

During the conversion of the thiosemicarbazones of phenanthraquinone and its derivatives into triazines a very slow evolution of hydrogen sulphide was noticed but no sulphur-free compound, as the product of a probable side-reaction, could be isolated. When, however, the 4-phenylthiosemicarbazone of phenanthraquinone was boiled in acetic acid for a long time copious hydrogen sulphide was evolved and a dark coloured solid free from sulphur was obtained. This substance contains an abnormally low percentage of nitrogen than what is demanded by the expected formula (IV).

The exact nature of the reaction as also similar other abnormal reactions which are being studied in other cases will be communicated in a subsequent paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenanthraquinone thiosemicarbazone.—It was prepared from phenanthraquinone and thiosemicarbazide in acetic acid solution, and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 212°. (Found: N, 14·82. C₁₅H₁₁ON₃S requires N, 14·94 per cent.).

3-Thiophenanthratiazine.—The above thiosemicarbazone was

heated in acetic acid solution for 30 hours, the solution gradually darkening in colour. During heating there was also noticed a slight evolution of hydrogen sulphide. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the residue was crystallised from pyridine in dull red rectangles, m. p. 198°. In spite of repeated searches no sulphur-free compound could be obtained. The same compound was also obtained from phenanthraquinone monoxime and thiosemicarbazide. The mixture was heated for 5 to 6 hours during which a dark coloured precipitate gradually separated which after being boiled with acetic acid was crystallised from pyridine. It is insoluble in acetic acid, alcohol and benzene but readily soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene. (Found: N, 16.10. $C_{15}H_9N_3S$ requires N, 15.97 per cent.).

2-Nitrophenanthraquinone thiosemicarbazone was prepared as before from 2-nitrophenanthraquinone and crystallised from pyridine in red rectangles, m. p. 234-235°. It is insoluble in alcohol and benzene; slightly soluble in acetic acid but readily so in hot pyridine. (Found: N, 17.31. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 17.18 per cent.).

3-Thiol-6-nitrophenanthrotriazine.—The above thiosemicarbazone was heated in acetic acid suspension for 35 hours when the deep red colour became dirty red. The solid was separated, boiled with pyridine to remove any unchanged thiosemicarbazone. The residue could not be crystallised from the ordinary organic solvents. The same compound was obtained by heating for 8 to 10 hours a mixture of 2-nitrophenanthraquinone monoxime and thiosemicarbazide; m. p. above 300°. It dissolves in nitrobenzene from which, however, it does not separate. (Found: N, 18.00. $C_{15}H_8O_2N_4S$ requires N, 18.18 per cent.).

2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinone thiosemicarbazone was prepared as before from 2:7-dinitrophenanthraquinone. From the clear solution a red precipitate separated. This was recrystallised from the minimum quantity of acetic acid in brown rectangles, m. p. 258°. (Found: N, 19.00. $C_{15}H_9O_2N_5S$ requires N, 18.87 per cent.).

3-Thiol-6:11-dinitrophenanthrotriazine.—The above thiosemicarbazone was heated in acetic acid solution for 20 hours. As the reaction proceeded a brown solid separated. This was filtered hot and the residue, after being boiled with acetic acid, was crystallised from pyridine in brown rectangles, m. p. 220°. The same compound was also obtained by heating an acetic acid solution of 2:7-dinitrophenanthraquinone monoxime and thiosemicarbazide for 4 hours. It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene and acetic acid but readily soluble in hot

pyridine. (Found: N, 19·72. $C_{15}H_7O_4N_3S$ requires N, 19·88 per cent.)

4-Nitrophenanthraquinone thiosemicarbazone was prepared as before from 4-nitrophenanthraquinone. The clear acetic acid solution obtained was diluted with water when a reddish-brown solid was precipitated. This was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol; m. p. 145°. (Found: N, 17·00. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 17·18 per cent.)

3-Thiol-8-nitrophenanthratrigine.—A solution of 4-nitrophenanthraquinone monoxime and thiosemicarbazido hydrochloride was heated for 6 to 7 hours. The solid that separated was filtered hot, boiled with acetic acid and crystallised from pyridine in brown rectangles; m. p. 230°. It is insoluble in acetic acid and alcohol but easily soluble in pyridine. (Found: N, 18·39. $C_{15}H_8O_2N_4S$ requires N, 18·18 per cent.)

3-Hydroxyphenanthrotriazine.—Phenanthraquinone semicarbazone was heated in acetic acid solution for 15 to 16 hours. The solid product obtained was filtered and crystallised from alcohol; m. p. 287°. (Found: N, 17·21. $C_{15}H_9ON_3$ requires N, 17·00 per cent.)

8-Nitro-3-hydroxyphenanthrotriazine.—4-Nitrophenanthraquinone-semicarbazone was heated as before in acetic acid solution for 25 hours. The solid product was crystallised from alcohol; m. p. 286°. (Found: N, 19·39. $C_{15}H_8O_3N_4$ requires N, 19·19 per cent.)

2:7-Dibromophenanthraquinone semicarbazone was prepared from 2:7-dibromophenanthraquinone and semicarbazido hydrochloride in yellow needles, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 10·04. $C_{15}H_9O_2N_3Br_2$ requires N, 9·93 per cent.)

6:11-Dibromo-3-hydroxyphenanthratrizine.—The above semicarbazone was suspended in acetic acid and heated for 10 hours when it gradually went into solution from which a light yellow crystalline mass separated. This was crystallised from alcohol in yellow rectangles, m. p. 295°. (Found: N, 10·52. $C_{15}H_7ON_3Br_2$ requires N, 10·37 per cent.)

Phenanthraquinone phenylthiosemicarbazone was obtained from phenanthraquinone and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazido as a red crystalline precipitate. This crystallised from pyridine in orange-red needles, m. p. 206°. (Found: N, 11·85. $C_{21}H_{15}ON_3S$ requires N, 11·76 per cent.)

When the above thiosemicarbazone was heated for about 30 hours in acetic acid suspension copious hydrogen sulphide was evolved

and the thiosemicarbazone gradually went into solution and at the same time a dark coloured solid separated. This was filtered hot, boiled with acetic acid and the residue crystallised from nitrobenzene in dark plates with a green lustre, m. p. above 300° . With the exception of nitrobenzene, it is insoluble in all other ordinary organic solvents. An analysis of the compound shows that it contains 4.93 per cent. of nitrogen.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
Dacca University.

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